

Historical Importance of Cuddalore through Archaeological Evidences – A Study

Dr. N. Dhanasekaran,

Guest Lecturer, Department of History,
Arignar Anna Government Arts College,
Villupuram-605 602, Tamil Nadu, India

ABSTRACT

This study has focused to reveal the historical importance of Cuddalore through Archaeological evidences. Archaeological sources are depicted the life and livelihood of the people from Cuddalore on Ancient period. Tamil Nadu is situated in the Southern part of India having unique culture and tradition. There are lot of inscriptions, archaeological evidence existed in this region and exhibited the history of the ancestors. On the path, Cuddalore also having the number of archaeological excavation sites and exploration evidences witnessed the life and livelihood of the archaic period. Geographical advantage made the inhabitants survived in this region through the ages. Thus, Cuddalore become the prominent place in Tamil Nadu during the ancient period which reflects the Archaeological evidence.

Keywords: Archaeological evidences, Cuddalore region, life and livelihood, Geographical advantages.

Introduction

This study has focused to reveal the historical importance of Cuddalore thorough Archaeological evidences. Archaeological sources are depicted the live and livelihood of the people from Cuddalore on Ancient period. These sources could be finding in the form of exploration and excavation. By analyzing the Archaeological sources means to get the knowledge about the hunting and gathering method, their settlement, agriculture and the writing system. The graffiti marks explain the unique history in this region. Both Archaeological department and individuals identified the antiquities, and identified the excavations sites like Iranji, Sengamedu, Palayapattinam, Karaikadu and Kudikadu.¹ Some of the goods were relatively similar to the Persia. It shows that the trade activities were prevailed in this region during ancient period. Also the imperial kingship was extended to the Cuddalore by the Choals, Pallavas, Sathavahanas and Kalabras. In a meantime some of the feudatories like Malayamans administrated in the Cuddalore region.

Pre-Historic Period

The primitive men who lived in the hilly region and caves during the prehistoric period gradually, he learned to make permanent settlements and do agriculture. Also, he used the stone tools for cultivation and other purposes. Generally, early inhabitation or industrial remnants were depicted in hilly or forested areas. However, some plains areas shared the same culture and traditions, particularly near the coast, as Tamil Nadu. The Stone Age has been classified into three periods: the Paleolithic, Mesolithic, and Neolithic. Paleolithic antiquities dating from 10,000 B.C. to 2,000 B.C. were discovered in various locations throughout Tamil Nadu.

²Ottankuppam, in Vridhachalam taluk, is the only place in Cuddalore district where the evidence can be found. ²

Neolithic period

In the cultural history of mankind, the Neolithic age marks the concluding stage of stone tool culture. The Neolithic age is characterized by the introduction of more evolved and developed typo-technological features. Man progressed from the "gathering stage" to the "producing stage."⁴ In India, the Neolithic period was dated around 8000 B.C. In South India, there were dates ranging from 2900 B.C. to 1000 B.C. ⁵During this period, humans settled in a particular place and domesticated the animals. In Tamil Nadu, the Neolithic sites were identified in Vellore, Dharmapuri, Krishnagiri, Salem, and Tiruvannamalai. In Cuddalore district, there are three Neolithic sites (Neolithic culture) identified after the excavation made by State Archaeology in Tamil Nadu, namely Kandarakkottai, Madur, and Karaimedu.⁶ The Neolithic tools excavated at the site of Karaimedu reveal the significance of Cuddalore. ⁶This source authenticates that human civilization emerged in the river valleys, and indeed, Cuddalore gave the opportunity for the permanent settlement of primitive men.

Karaimedu(Archaeological site)

The Karaimedu exploration and excavation reports revealed the significance of Cuddalore taluk. Karaimedu is located on the way of Villupuram from Pondicherry, in Cuddalore taluk. The rudimentary period of this thesis begins with the Neolithic period because the known sources from this site have been excavated. The Neolithic stone tools discovered during

excavation in the Karaimedu confirmed prehistoric human habitation. This tool may have a polished appearance, which may indicate that it is from a later period.⁷

A huge mound held at Karaimedu, which local villagers dug them for the water way to the pond. While they identified the some ancient artifacts there, especially ring wells. Then the Archaeologists have explored this site with the advice of local villages, and dug the trench around 1X1 m. The exploration given the results of many ring wells discovered. Further the exploration made up to the level of 1.5m, and four more rings were identified. Earlier, the villagers identified the broken bones, broken dished at the bottom level. The rings are in red colour, with the size of around 80 cm (diameter). In ancient era, the ring wells were used for brought the drinking water near the rivers and pond areas. Then these rings wells used for the burial purpose, finally used as dust bins. However, the complete excavation not made till date. In further excavation has given the great vision of ancient life and livelihood of Cuddalore region.⁸

Chalcolithic period

The usage of Copper-Bronze by the humans categorized as Chalcolithic period, which comes after the Neolithic period.⁹ However, the excavations at Neolithic sites in Tamil Nadu have not yielded any significant copper-bronze objects. This leads to the conclusion that in Tamil Nadu, the Iron Age succeeded the Neolithic Period by passing the Chalcolithic Period.

Iron Age -Megalithic

More than half of the nearly 120 sites were excavated in Tamil Nadu so far date from the Iron Age. The exploration and excavation carried out in the northern wedge of Tamil Nadu, particularly in the river valleys of Palar, Pennaiyar, Kaveri, Vaigai, and Tamiraparani, yielded

clear evidence for staving off the Iron Age in Tamil Nadu.⁹ Excavation in the lower Pennaiyar valley in the Cuddalore region revealed Iron Age colonization, but the region has not seen any cultural outbreaks to date.¹⁰

Early Historic

The letters were identified in the pots, caves, and mountain walls described as Early Historic. The evolution of letters and scripts given the historical resources, between 500 B.C to 500 A.D., These periods has renowned in the history of Tamil Nadu as ‘Sangam Age’, also it has other names like “Indo-Roman period” and “Megalithic Age”.¹¹ The early historic period are classified into three phases, first one covered the period of pre-historic to 1st century B.C. The second one is covered into 1st century B.C to 3rd century A.D., The final one covered the period of 3rd to 6th centuries. Indo-Roman trade (maritime) coinciding the first two phases and third one deals Post-Sangam Age.¹² The Chalcolithic period have a unique feature, which depicts the artifacts of pottery, especially black and red colour. Also it has unique identity like red exterior and black interior which found in India. Iron Age is classified into the period between 1000 B.C and 300 B.C, and early history covers the period 300 B.C and 500 A.D.

Early historic sites in the South Arcot District

The South Arcot region(before bifurcation), had the several evidences about the ring wells, brick structures, beads, terracotta lamps, punch-marked coins, Roman coins, coins of Malayamans, and Rouletted Ware.

Karaikadu(Archaeological site)

Karaikadu geographical nature is the major significance, which located in the backwaters of Uppanar. This had to given the prosperity to anchorage the boats easier. In 1966 A.D., the Archaeological Survey of India made an initiative to excavate the site of Karaikadu. At the time of excavation, there were several plants grown there. So the excavation was made by the team of Archaeologist in small areas in the site. Further this excavation was continued by the Department of Archaeology, University of Madras in 1989 A.D.,

The exaction has given the artifacts of archaic period, especially the potteries both local and imported. Moreover, these potteries were more resemble of the other site of Arikamedu. The excavation have unearthed other things like conch shell artifacts, fragments of imported amphora jars, Roman-styled roulette pottery, conical jars, unearthed bricks and coins.²⁰ Further, this site includes the iron slag utilized for glass manufacture, crucibles, and terracotta pipes. The semi-precious stone beads and yellow glass beads manufactures in the sites, exhibited the various stage of glass manufacturing in ancient period. This glass beads is also very similar to the Arikamedu site at Pondicherry. Perhaps, the glass beads was manufactured in Arikamedu, and sent to the Karaikadu site. A brick structure was identified which promptly related to the bead-making industry existed in the archaic period. These artificates has given the conclusion about the archaeologists, and it belongs to the period of 1st century A.D., like other site of Arikamedu. Arikamedu has the source of human habitation during the medieval period. The relationship with the Arikamedu and Karaikadu more prominent in the archaic period could be the extension of the site of Arikamedu.¹³

Fine gold Roman coins, red conical jars, and amphora shreds were discovered at the Karaikadu site .The literary sources of the Sangam period, the periplus of the Erythraean Sea,

witnessed the spatial distribution of ancient ports along the Indian coast. It significantly recalled Ptucceri (Poduke), Karaikkai, Tondi, and Musiri. Karaikadu is a town about 30 kilometres from Arikamedu. It is located at a distance of 5 kilometres from Cuddalore. It is located on the East Coast. Firstly, this site had excavated by Yves Martain of the Institut de Physique du Globe, Paris for French Institute of Pondicherry.

Kudikadu(Archaeological site)

Kudikadu is located near the Karaikadu site in Cuddalore taluk in the Paravanr river basin. K.V. Raman made an attempt to explore and excavate the Kudikdu site with the help of the University of Madras. This location is on the east coast of Tamil Nadu, 10 kilometres near the town of Cuddalore, on the east coast road. The huge mound identified in this region which covering 2 to 3.5 metres heights, and also covering this site near 90 acres. At present (2022) the SIPCOT industries worked under this region, and renowned as ‘SIPCOT industrial complex’. The Archaeological excavation made two places known as KDU-1 and KDU-2. Both are excavated different points, and cutting was carried down to the soil which up to 2.5 m at KDU-1 and KDU-2 under 3.2 m.

All the excavation report says that, the deposits represented a uniformity could be belongs to the single cultural period. The ceramic verities are found in this site like amphorae pieces and Roulette ware are significant, coloured black, black-and-red ware, and red-slipped ware. It characterizes were polished nature. The artifacts recovered from this site with glass beads, semiprecious stones, human figurine, terracotta, a votive lamp, ear ornament, hopscotch, games, a copper pendant, and iron objects. Along with the artifacts, the raw materials which was used for the manufacturing the glass, different types of semiprecious stones also found high

volume. In KDU-2 had a burnt brick wall, depth of 0.47 m, and 0.70 m wide running towards the east west direction revealed. The excavation produced some results indicating that the wall extended beyond the trench; this could be determined with additional research. Despite this, the department has yet to conduct an excavation after many years.

The size of burnt bricks use for the construction was 35x22x6 cm, which very similar to the other sites of Appukallu, Kanchipuram, Urayiyur and Kaveriperumpattinam. Also this site having the incomplete beads, associated with the beadmaking industry. The same site , at a depth of 0.7m level had the postholds, which also confirm the above statement. This sources has clarify the date of the site, which belongs to first century B.C to second century A.D. ²⁸The remains have been identified in Kudikadu tells the significance of the region, and it was a contemporary of Arikamedu, the ancient town of Pondicherry. It is obvious from this concentrate that Gudikadu was a studio for making interesting stone globules. It is also one of the proofs of Tamil Nadu's trade relations with the Romans. The literary works during the Sangam period give us detailed information regarding the advancement of architecture and the usage of bricks. Bricks were used to build architectural structures and were known as *Suduman* during the Sangam Age, according to "Perumpanattrupadai," a work of Sangam literature. ¹⁴

Factory-oriented premises

Bead making

In India, there are 135 sites identified by the archaeology department that have evidence of glass and glass beads dating from 300 BCE to 400 BCE. In the first and second centuries A.D., there were six places famous for making beads in the Indo-Pacific, namely OC Eo in

Vietnam, Kuala Selinsing in Malaysia, Mantai in Sri Lanka, Khlong Thom in Thailand, Arikamedu in Pondicherry, and Karaikadu in Cuddalore. As described, the evidence for glass bead manufacture is most evocative at three early Tamil sites: Arikamedu, Porunthal, and Kariakadu. On those days, these modern Indo-Pacific bead-making sites were linked.

Beads are typically made by winding, then dipping, then drawing, then mould pressing, then marvering, then cutting, then grinding, and even drilling, or by a combination of these methods. The pellucid dark blue glass beads at Kariakadu and Arikamedu contain high levels of manganese, which includes 1.5 percent potassium and a trace of cobalt to produce the color. The Karaikadu yielded coins of Roman and indigenous origin, ceramics, and beads reported to be similar to those from Manthai, Anuradahapura, Kelaniya, Ridiyagama, and Tissamaharama. A number of beads of caprious stones like chalcedony, crystal, jasper, carnelian and agate, are manufactured and found in the strata. This evidence indicates that the Cuddalore region was an important place in the ancient period, with factories producing items such as beads.¹⁵

Other sites near Cuddalore

Manikolai

This site Manikolai is about 30 kilometres from Cuddalore town (near Otttathai village) on the Cuddalore-Chidambaram highway. Potsherds of red and black pottery, fine red pottery, coarse red pottery, and grey pottery were discovered during the exploration in a cultivation field opposite the Modern CSI Church. In addition to potsherds, a huge number of glass beads and rough edges were poised from the same location. The glass beads in distinct shapes and fickle colors, which typically include green, lack, dull red, dark blue, and violet, , and yellow, show

affinity with the Arikamedu bead detection. The prominent area of the site is 2 ha. The Manikollai beads are comparatively similar to Karaikadu, and Giribawa. But these beads do not match those from Arikamedu. These pieces of evidence revealed that different techniques were used to make the beads.

Thirusopuram

Thirusopuram is about 15 kilometers east of Cuddalore on the Cuddalore-Chidambarm road. The River Uppanar flourished the land of adjacent village of Thiyagavalli, near Cuddalore old town. Thiyagavalli could be the part of Chadurvedimangalm in the Later Chola period, which named after the Kulothuna Cholan's wife in 12th to 13th century A.D. Cholas temple existed in the premises exhibited the antiquity of the village. But the pre-historic antiquates are identified this village, in Chalimedu which close to the seashore by exploration. Chalimedu has number of red and black pottery shears, fine red pottery, and coarse red pottery. Moreover, the exploration and survey revealed the good glass beads. The glass beads were identified different colours, various shapes which typically from dull red, dark blue, yellow, violet and black, similar to the Arikamedu site.¹⁶

Ceramic industry

Three prominent ceramic industries were found in the Karaikadu region: black and red ware, red-slipped ware, and Roulette ware. Among them, the red and black pottery show to be meager in usage and rather coarse. There are simple bowls with a round base, among the marinated cooking vessels identified in this region. The roulette cloth was the characteristic fabric for fixing the chronological sphere. The roulette ware is identified in its different grey and

pink colour. These characteristics are exhibited the dishes with incurved sides and beaked rim. The routed ware is found in its typical pink and grey color. The characteristic types are dishes with a beaked rim and incurved sides. There was also wreck of conical-bottomed amphorae in bawdy red fabric. ¹⁷

Conclusion

Tamil Nadu is situated in the Southern part of India having unique culture and tradition. There are lot of inscriptions, archaeological evidence existed in this region and exhibited the history of the ancestors. On the path, Cuddalore also having the number of archaeological excavation sites and exploration evidences witnessed the life and livelihood of the archaic period. Geographical advantage made the inhabitants survived in this region through the ages. Thus, Cuddalore become the prominent place in Tamil Nadu during the ancient period which reflects the Archaeological evidence.

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